

CRYSTALLIZATION KINETICS OF CALCIUM HYDROSULFOALUMINATE DURING HARDENING OF MIXED HIGH-STRENGTH CEMENT.

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Annotation.

The work indicates based on the results of chemical, radiographic and differential thermal analyses – it can be concluded that additional introduction of CaSO₄ into the composition of high-strength cement contributes to a more intense crystallization of ettringite only on the first day of hardening, with time this process slows down, and the amount of ettringite does not increase.

Key words.

Crystallization, gypsum, calcium hydrosulfoaluminate, cement, hydrosulfoaluminate, ettringite, endoeffect, hydrosilicate gel.

With an insufficient amount of gypsum, the content of calcium hydrosulfoaluminate of a high-sulfate form in the stone of mixed sulfate-containing cements is insignificant. The strength of the structure containing free calcium hydroaluminate is high at an early age, but its presence in aggressive solutions is undesirable due to the formation of calcium hydrosulfoaluminates in a rigid structure. In this regard, the study of the influence of CaSO₄ and CaO separately on the crystallization kinetics of calcium hydrosulfoaluminate in the hardening of mixed high-strength cement is of particular interest. Experiments have shown that when 3 to 10% CaO is added to the cement, the process of water binding is accelerated, the content of bound water in samples made from mixed high-strength cement with the addition of CaO is much higher (from 5.42 to 14.76%) than in samples made without CaO additive:

Hydration time, 24 hours		$\frac{\text{HCV} + \text{CaO}(\%)}{97 + 3 \cdot 95 + 3 \cdot 90 + 10}$	$\frac{\text{HCV} + \text{CaSO}_4(\%)}{97 + 3 \cdot 95 + 3 \cdot 90 + 10}$
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1	10,2	11,2	11,6	16,8	11,4	12,1	12,4
3	12,1	13,5	13,8	4,1	12,1	14,0	13,2
7	13,3	-	-	16,3	-	-	17,5
14	-	-	-	18,3	-	-	17,9
28	16,4	-	-	31,7	-	-	18,0

This phenomenon is due to the rapid formation of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, which gradually crystallizes in the pores of the cement stone. $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ after 28 days - 0.03 and 0.08%, while the cement stone contains 18.3 and 19.9% free CaO , respectively.

On X-ray patterns of samples with the addition of 10% CaO hydrated for 3 and 7 days, intense diffraction reflections of calcium hydroxide ($d=4.92, 2.63.1.76 \text{ \AA}$) are found. The intensity of ettringite lines for this period of hydration is less than in the X-ray patterns of samples of mixed high-strength cement without the addition of CaO . By the 14th day CaO hydration and portlandite crystallization accelerate: a strong increase in the intensity of the interplanar maximum at 2.61 \AA is observed on the X-ray pattern, which is apparently due to the coincidence of the lines of belite (2.61 \AA) and calcium hydroxide (2.63 \AA). A significant increase in the intensity of the lines at 4.92 \AA , which is usually attributed to $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, is caused by the superposition of the line of calcium hydrosilicates on it. By this time, the intensity of ettringite lines ($d=9.81, 5.71, 3.86 \text{ \AA}$) does not change. This indicates that the growth of ettringite crystals and the increase in its amount does not occur until all calcium oxide is completely hydrated. After 28 days of storage in water, the amount of chemically bound water in the samples reaches 31.8%, i.e. the content of hydrate neoplasms is almost 2 times higher than their content in the cement stone of daily hardening. By this period, the intensity of the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ lines at 2.61 \AA does not change, while ettringite increases noticeably ($d=9.81, 5.71, 3.92 \text{ \AA}$). This indicates that, after 14 days, the hydration of CaO and the crystallization of portlandite are practically completed, and the crystallization of calcium trisulfate hydrosulfoaluminate is intensified. The increase in the content of chemically bound water after 28 days is also explained by the intensive formation of this mineral.

The monosulfate form of GSAK ($d=8.38 \text{ \AA}$) appears after the formation of ettringite at a later time of hardening (28 days). Comparing X-ray diffraction patterns of samples of high-strength cement with and without CaO , hydrated for 3.7 and 28 days, it can be seen that with the addition of 10% CaO , the formation of tobermorite gel slows down. Apparently, during hydration, the initially formed tricalcium hydrosilicate and calcium hydroxide in the form of a film envelop the original grain, blocking the access of water to it and thereby inhibiting the

hydration process, which can be resumed only after complete crystallization of Ca(OH)₂ in the pores of the cement stone. As L.G. Shpynova notes, in the structures of newly formed calcium hydrosilicates, octahedral layers of portlandite are one of the main elements. In gypsum-aluminous cement, in the very initial period of hydration (5-10 min), CaO, increasing the supersaturation of the liquid hardening cement, accelerates the interaction of gypsum with the aluminate component, which contributes to the crystallization of finely dispersed ettringite. Thus, for the complete binding of the entire amount of sulfoaluminate present in the composition of high-strength cement into ettringite, CaO is not required to be added to the composition of the mixed cement. This will lead to undesirable inhibition of the process of hydrolysis and hydration of C₃S, as well as to a slowdown in the crystallization of calcium hydrosulfaluminate in the initial stages of hardening. The introduction of anhydrous CaSO₄ into the composition of high-strength cement contributes to a more intense binding of water during the hardening process. In samples with 3, 5, 10% CaSO₄, the content of bound water in all periods of hardening is 2-4% higher than in samples without CaSO₄. This phenomenon is caused by relatively fast crystallization of trisulfate HSAA, which is confirmed by differential analysis data. The endoeffect at 150°C on the differential heating curve of cement hydrated in the presence of 5% CaSO₄ during the day is significantly greater than the same endoeffect on the differential heating curve of cement hydrated without CaSO₄. After 3 days of hardening, the dimensions of the endoeffects of both cements (with and without the addition of CaSO₄) at 160°C become almost the same. With an increase in the content of CaSO₄ up to 10%, the intensity of the endoeffect at 150°C, related to trisulfate HSAC, noticeably increases. Further hydration, apparently, since on the thermograms of samples hydrated for 3 days, the size of the endoeffect at 150°C does not change. By day 14, this effect shifts towards higher temperatures, which is explained by total dehydration

The data on the kinetics of water binding in the cement stone of the composition under consideration are in good agreement with the data on the kinetics of gypsum binding, since the main amount of water is spent on the crystallization of ettringite. The amount of the latter depends on the mineralogical composition of the initial SAS cement.

It should be noted that the intensity of ettringite lines ($d = 9.81, 5.65, 4.66, 3.86$ Å) in cement stone with the addition of 10% CaSO₄ is almost the same as without the addition. The presence of gypsum dihydrate is also indicated x-ray data ($d = 7.68, 4.30, 2.85$ Å) of samples of 28-day hardening. Strengthening of the line at

$d=2.85$ Å is explained by the superposition of lines of non-hydrated calcium sulfosilicate at $d=2.84$ Å on it.

Thus, the additional introduction of CaSO_4 into the composition of high-strength cement contributes to a more intense crystallization of ettringite only on the first day of hardening, with time this process slows down, and the amount of ettringite does not increase. Excess CaSO_4 is hydrated and crystallizes into liquid. Excess CaSO_4 hydrates and crystallizes in the pores of the cement stone in the form of $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The addition of gypsum leads to morphological changes in the hydration product and to the transition of part of the sulfate into the gel lattice. The presence of a line at $d = 11.35$ Å on the X-ray pattern can be explained by the appearance of a hydrosilicate gel, the lattice of which contains sulfate ions.

Based on the results of chemical, X-ray and differential thermal analyzes, it can be concluded that the additional introduction of CaO into the composition of high-strength cement slows down the process of hydration and hydrolysis of C3S and the crystallization of ettringite in the initial stages of hardening, and CaSO_4 , on the contrary, accelerates the crystallization of ettringite in the first day, slowing down in subsequent ones. During hydration of mixed cement with CaO or CaSO_4 , as well as without them, ettringite is formed at different times in the amount and at a rate depending on the mineralogical composition of the cement.

LITERATURE:

1. Отакузиев Т.А, Эгамбердиев М.С Минерализующее влияние некоторых солей на обжиг сульфоалюминатно-силикатного цемента. European journal of science archive conferences series. Germany July august, 2021. 4-8p.
2. Egamberdiev M.S. The use of helium coatings in the production of concrete works // Concrete and reinforced concrete. - 1989. - No. 9. - S. 13-14.
3. Эгамбердиев М.С., Убайдуллаева Н.Ф. Мьморчиликда психологиянинг ахамияти.// Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве. 2021/1 338-340б.
4. Egamberdiev M.S. Technological method of making cast -in-place concrete structures typical of Central Asian climatic conditions.// Web of scientist: international scientific research journal. 7-11 p. ISSN:2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue5, May., 2022